

TWO LAYER COMPOSITE SHELL FOR ANCHORED REFRACTORY LINING COMPUTING

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SUMMARY: In circulating fluidized bed combustors, the refractory linings anchored to the steel structure (casing) are submitted to important thermal loading which conducts to cracking (due to the difference between the thermal coefficients). A first approach allows to analyse the problem at the anchor scale: a smeared crack model allows to compute the damage which is observed in an experimental test. But since a boiler or a cyclone contains thousand of anchors, it is not possible to compute a complete structure with this model. So, an approach was developed with a two-layer shell equivalent to the anchored lining and the casing. This model was identified with an inverse method, using results from the first approach and validated by a bending test performed on a refractory lining specimen.

KEYWORDS: two layer composite shell finite element, smeared crack model, thermal loading, inverse identification, metallic anchor, refractory lining.

INTRODUCTION

The aim of this study is the numerical prediction of the refractory lining behaviour under thermal solicitations in a circulating fluidized bed combustor" (CFBC). In this boiler, the refractory castable is anchored to the steel support structure (casing). Because of temperature gradient and thermal expansion difference between castable and metal, high level stress occurs within the castable, on heating or cooling, and may lead to failure. To compute a structure like a boiler or a cyclone, it is not possible to take a 3D finite element model because there are thousands of anchors. Presented solution is to build a two layer composite shell element to simplify the finite element model. An orthotropic material is the component of the first layer which models the casing. The second layer models the damageable anchored refractory castable. The behaviour of this shell element must be equivalent to the behaviour of the casing, the linings and the anchors.

Three scales can be defined for this problem. The first is the scale of the anchor, the second the scale of a panel with several anchors (meso-scale), and the third is the scale of the structure (macro-scale). The shell element is built at the meso-scale. For this, it is necessary to have informations from the scale of the anchor. Therefore, the first step is to model the behaviour around one anchor [1] [2].

STUDY AT THE SCALE OF AN ANCHOR

Model

The behaviour of one anchor embedded in a panel of castable is modelled in 3D. The steel behaviour is elastic-plastic. The behaviour of the refractory castable is elastic-plastic in compression, and elastic-damageable in tension, with softening after the elastic part [3] (Figure 1). To model this damageable behaviour with softening, a smeared crack model is used [4][5][6]. The cracks are taken into account as a loss of stiffness and not as macro-cracks: the displacement u_{ck} due to the crack opening is transformed in strain ϵ_{ck} with a characteristic length h :

$$\epsilon_{ck} = \frac{u_{ck}}{h} \quad (1)$$

It is a "multiple fixed crack model", i.e. the crack directions are fixed, but it is possible to have three orthogonal cracks in 3D. The crack detection surface is shown in 2D figure 1.

Fig. 1: Uniaxial tension behaviour and shape of the crack detection surface.

Identification

The castable tension behaviour is identified using a four point bending test [7], linked with an inverse method. Indeed, a bending test is a structural test with tension and compression. The principle of the inverse identification is described below.

Let us define:

- p: the number of parameters to determine,
- \mathbf{m} : the vector containing the p parameters,
- n_{ex} : the number of experimental values.

The vector \mathbf{r} (difference between the finite element prediction and the experimental results) is given by :

$$r_i = F^{EF}(\epsilon_i^{ex}) - F^{ex}(\epsilon_i^{ex}) \quad \text{for } i = 1 \text{ to } n_{ex} \quad (2)$$

where $F^{EF}(\epsilon_i^{ex})$ and $F^{ex}(\epsilon_i^{ex})$ are respectively the calculated (finite element prediction) and experimental forces for a same experimental strain ϵ_i^{ex} for a given value of \mathbf{m} .

We define the error function (least square) as:

$$E(\mathbf{m}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{ex}} [r_i(\mathbf{m})]^2 = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{r} \quad (3)$$

The researched parameters must minimise this error function $E(\mathbf{m})$. This problem has only a solution if the number of experimental values n_{ex} is higher than the number of parameters p . Furthermore, some parameters must stay in acceptable limits (for example, the Young's modulus must be positive). These constraints are written as following:

$$C_j(\mathbf{m}) \geq 0, \quad j = 1 \text{ to } q, \text{ where } q \text{ is the number of constraints.}$$

They are introduced in $E(\mathbf{m})$ to obtain a new error function $E^*(\mathbf{m})$:

$$E^*(\mathbf{m}) = E(\mathbf{m}) + \sum_{j=1}^q \frac{\omega_j}{C_j(\mathbf{m})} \quad (4)$$

where ω_j is the weight of the constraint j .

One notes:

$$\xi_j = \frac{\omega_j}{C_j(\mathbf{m})} \quad (5)$$

The ξ_j have only a contribution to $E^*(\mathbf{m})$ if some parameters are near from the limits of their admissible domain. The parameters must stay into this domain, so the ξ_j are always positive.

The Levenberg-Marquardt method [8] was used to minimise the error function $E^*(\mathbf{m})$. This method is iterative and uses a positive scalar parameter λ which is adjusted to have a decreasing of $E^*(\mathbf{m})$ at each iteration. This method was modified to take into account the constraints [9].

To begin the resolution, an initial set of parameters $\mathbf{m}(0)$ and weights ω_j are chosen.

At the iteration k , the evolution of the parameters $d\mathbf{m}$ is given by:

$$\left[(\mathbf{J}^{(k)})^T (\mathbf{J}^{(k)}) + \lambda^{(k)} \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{H}^{(k)} \right] d\mathbf{m}^{(k)} = -(\mathbf{J}^{(k)})^T \mathbf{r}^{(k)} + \mathbf{f}^{(k)} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } J_{i\alpha} = \frac{\partial r_i}{\partial m_\alpha} = \frac{\partial F_i^{EF}}{\partial m_\alpha} \quad (7)$$

$$f_{\alpha} = -\sum_{j=1}^q \frac{\partial \xi_j}{\partial m_{\alpha}} = \sum_{j=1}^q \frac{\omega_j}{C_j^2} \left(\frac{\partial C_j}{\partial m_{\alpha}} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$H_{\alpha\beta} = \sum_{j=1}^q \frac{\partial^2 \xi_j}{\partial m_{\alpha} \partial m_{\beta}} \approx \sum_{j=1}^q \frac{\omega_j}{C_j^3} \left[2 \left(\frac{\partial C_j}{\partial m_{\alpha}} \right) \left(\frac{\partial C_j}{\partial m_{\beta}} \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

with

$i = 1$ to n_{ex} (number of experimental values)

$\alpha, \beta = 1$ to p (number of parameters)

$j = 1$ to q (number of constraints).

The jacobian matrix \mathbf{J} is calculated using a finite difference method. For a given set of parameters \mathbf{m} , the finite element model gives the response. The parameter m_{α} is perturbed from a value δm_{α} . $J_{i\alpha}$ is then given by:

$$J_{i\alpha} = \frac{F_i^{\text{EF}}(m_{\alpha} + \delta m_{\alpha}) - F_i^{\text{EF}}(m_{\alpha})}{\delta m_{\alpha}} \quad (10)$$

At each iteration it is necessary to perturb all parameters one after the other, that is to perform p finite element calculations.

If the softening curve (Figure 1) is taken as a straight line to simplify, there are three parameters to identify in tension: the Young's modulus, the slope of the softening curve and the maximum value of stress σ_t^u .

Experimental study

Fig. 2: Experimental devices for thermal cycling (a) and pull-out tests (b).

To validate the model, some experimental tests were performed on panels with one or two anchors. A special furnace (Figure 2a) was built to reproduce the thermo-mechanical conditions of the refractory linings in the CFBC boiler (850°C on the inner-face, 350°C on the back-face). Acoustic emission (Figure 3) was used to follow the crack opening around the anchor. It shows that the first cycle is the most damaging for the castable, and it is possible to determine the temperature of the first cracking and to compare the damage level between to

moments of the process. But it does not give quantitative values of damage. So, some pull-out tests were performed (Figure 2b). The decrease of the stiffness shows the increase of damage around the anchor.

Fig. 3: Acoustic emission on an anchored panel: inner-face temperature (curve 1), back-face temperature (curve 2), and acoustic emission (curve 3).

Simulations

The simulations of thermal loading on panels with one (Figure 4) or two (Figure 5) axisymmetric anchors show that the crack directions are mostly radial, like the experimental observations. The temperature of first cracking is the same that the one given by acoustic emission. The simulations of a pull-out test on a panel which was previously submitted to thermal loading shows a loss of stiffness in agreement with the tests.

Fig. 4: Simulation of the damaged zone

Fig. 5: Modelling of one quarter of a panel with two linked anchors, and stresses 11.

MODELLING AT THE SCALE OF THE STRUTURE

Two layer composite shell

Fig. 6: Modelling of a 3D cell (lining, anchors and casing) with an equivalent two layer shell element, and identification with an inverse method.

Fig. 7: One quarter of the studied structure (lining, anchors and casing with tubes).

The previous model can not be used to compute a structure with thousand of anchors. So, it is necessary to build a simplified element: a shell element with two layers (Figure 6). The first layer has an elastic-orthotropic behaviour (casing), the second layer an elastic-damageable behaviour (refractory linings), the same one than the castable, but with other parameters. To identify the parameters of the shell element it is necessary to have several tests on structures with several anchors and tubes. But they are difficult to perform (the specimens are very big). So, we choose to simulate this different tests (tension, bending and shear) on a structure (Figure 7) using the model at the scale of an anchor. The parameters are identified with the

same inverse method described above. The numerical tests give the "experimental datas". One experimental bending test will be performed to validate this approach.

Cyclone computing

The first application of this two layer composite shell is the computing of a cyclone (which separates hot gases from circulating bed of ash, and abrasive material) (Figure 8). It is submitted to the real thermal loading: 850°C for the inner-face and 350°C for the back-face. Figure 9 shows the circumferential stresses in six points of the thickness of the shell element with linear and non linear computation. It shows the importance of damage: the stress sign in the orthotropic layer is the opposite with respect to a linear calculation.

Fig. 8: Mesh of a cyclone, integration points in the shell thickness and thermal loading.

Fig. 9: Circumferential stresses in the thickness of one shell element at the integration points for linear (a) and non linear (b) calculations.

CONCLUSIONS

To obtain a problem that can be numerically solved, it is necessary to use a simplified finite element to compute a part of a CFBC structure. This element is a shell with an orthotropic layer and a damageable layer. Its characteristics were identified with simulations performed at a smaller scale. This model at the scale of an anchor was validated with thermal loading and pull-out tests.

The first simulation performed on a cyclone showed that it is important to take into account the damage in the refractory linings in the computation of such a structure : the stresses are

completely modified with respect to an elastic approach. So, it is then possible to have a tool to help the design of refractory lining structures.

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